

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE STRESS TRANSFER IN DISCONTINUOUS COMPOSITES ON THE BASIS OF A UNIT CELL MODEL

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ABSTRACT

In this study, composites with discontinuous ‘brick-and-mortar’ architecture, consisting of conceptually stiff load-carrying bricks connected by a mortar material, were treated. The bricks were composed of unidirectional pre-impregnated tapes with a thermoplastic matrix, and a very thin interface of thermoplastic material represented the mortar. The problem was simplified to a unit cell containing a single overlap between two bricks, where the stresses between the bricks are transferred purely by shear in the mortar material. The stress-strain response of the unit cell in tension was determined by experiments and compared to predictions by a numerical model available from literature, which is based on shear-lag stress transfer. The results showed that it is possible to create a highly non-linear stress-strain response with this ordered discontinuous architecture. The effect of the interface shear strength and fracture toughness and the influence of the brick geometry on the achievable tensile strength were discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Current applications of composite materials primarily include thin shells and continuous profiles, which are traditionally manufactured on the approach of a layered structure (laminate). One drawback associated with laminates is their sudden and possibly catastrophic failure. Recent effort has been directed towards developing random discontinuous composites manufactured by compression moulding of chopped pre-impregnated tapes [1-3]. Such discontinuous materials may be used to produce complex 3D shapes, for applications such as load introduction with the possibility of a more gradual failure [4].

Due to the discontinuous nature of these materials, stresses are transferred between the fibre-reinforced chips by shear in the interface, which is usually formed by the matrix material. The fact that the mesostructure is developed randomly raises difficulty to study the stress transfer in full detail; this challenge has not yet been solved in the literature. Models on the basis of a simplified geometric representation of the composite, such as a unit cell containing an overlap of two chips, may aid the development of fundamental understanding. The influence of different chip orientation, overlap length and matrix material can be studied separately in this manner.

Stress transfer between discontinuous fibres embedded in a matrix has often been modelled by the shear-lag theory, as first introduced to fibrous composite materials by Cox [5] and soon afterwards applied to unidirectional laminates by Hedgepeth [6]. The shear lag model assumes that tensile carrying elements (fibres or plies) are connected by purely shear-carrying material (matrix).

A shear lag model which was adapted to represent discontinuous composites with a staggered architecture (‘brick-and-mortar’) has recently been published by Pimenta and Robinson [4]. As

outlined above, they state that a ductile behaviour can be introduced by using a discontinuous architecture. They used a unit cell representation containing a single overlap of two plies (bricks) connected by a shear-carrying matrix (mortar). The model permits to predict the stress-strain response as well as the fibre and matrix stress distribution of a brick-and-mortar composite, using a generic piecewise-linear matrix material and including fracture. An experimental validation for a discontinuous carbon/epoxy composite was published by Czel et al. [7], where a good agreement between model and experiments was found. On the other hand, no experimental studies dealing with thermoplastic matrix materials exist.

In this work we attempted to investigate the stress transfer and the stress-strain response of aforementioned brick-and-mortar composite with a thermoplastic mortar material. We expect to achieve a different response with a thermoplastic mortar material as compared to a thermoset mortar material such as epoxy, since thermoplastics generally exhibit ductile behaviour, whereas a brittle behaviour is more typically associated with thermosets. We focused our studies on composites made from glass fiber (GF) and Polyamide 12 (PA12). One particular aim was to study the occurrence of a non-linear and possibly pseudo-ductile response.

2 UNIT CELL MODEL

2.1 Geometric representation

The geometry considered in this study is the ‘brick-and-mortar’ architecture, where stiff load-carrying bricks are embedded in mortar which transfers the loads between the bricks purely by shear, see Figure 1. In our case, discontinuous plies of unidirectional GF/PA12 prepreg form the bricks, and a thin layer of PA12 represents the mortar. The ‘brick-and-mortar’ architecture can be simplified to a unit cell, as illustrated by the green box in Figure 1, which contains an overlap of two plies with the connecting matrix material. Figure 1 shows the characteristic dimensions in the unit cell, $l_{Overlap}$ and $t_{Overlap}$, which are one half of the respective dimension of the brick, L_{Brick} and T_{Brick} . The problem inside the unit cell is symmetric about the central point, as indicated by the small dash.

Figure 1: Illustration of the unit cell

2.2 Numerical modelling

Shear lag theory can be used to predict the shear stress in the mortar and the tensile stress in the bricks. In general, the theory predicts an inhomogeneous shear stress distribution for an applied tensile loading. Stress concentrations occur at the ends of the bricks, whereas in the centre of the overlap, the stress approaches a lower plateau value. The tensile strength of a single overlap, presuming failure in the mortar (or interface), is mainly dependent on the aspect ratio and the elastic modulus of the bricks, the shear modulus as well as the strength of the mortar. Since the ‘brick-and-mortar’ composite consists of repetitions of the unit cell, the tensile strength and the stress-strain response of the composite are equal to that of the overlap in the unit cell.

The aim of the numerical modelling was to predict the stress-strain response of the unit cell geometry considered in this study, which can then be compared to experimental results. We based our modelling on the shear-lag formulation proposed by Pimenta and Robinson [4], with kind permission

by the authors. This model was used because it overcomes the usual assumption of a linear elastic mortar material, as a generic piece-wise linear constitutive law can be incorporated. In addition, it allows varying the size and aspect ratio of the bricks, so that the influence on the strength can be investigated. The nominal material properties used in the modelling are listed in Table 1.

Brick tensile modulus E_{Brick}	Mortar shear modulus G_{Mortar}	Mortar shear strength S_{Mortar}	Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IIc}
<i>47.8 GPa</i>	<i>1 GPa</i>	<i>45 MPa</i>	<i>3 kJ/m²</i>

Table 1: Nominal material properties

The brick tensile modulus was determined from mechanical tests (see Section 3.2). The mortar shear modulus was estimated, as no data was accessible in the literature and its influence was found to be low in a parametric study. The mortar shear strength was chosen based on the interlaminar shear strength reported in [8], and the interlaminar fracture toughness was obtained from [9].

The points of the piece-wise linear constitutive law are shown in Table 2, where γ is the shear strain and τ the shear stress of the mortar. No full stress-strain curves in shear were available from literature, hence the constitutive law was approximated by a tri-linear material model using the nominal properties listed above. The 3rd point was set so as to represent moderate strain hardening and a relatively ductile behaviour. The last point was adjusted such as to ensure a correct energy dissipation associated with the formation of a crack tip [4].

Point	0	1	2	3
γ (abs.)	0	0.04	0.2	26.53
τ (MPa)	0	40	45	0

Table 2: Points of the piece-wise linear mortar constitutive law

2.3 Strength estimation

Two approximations regarding the overlap strength in the unit cell exist: 1) the yield-slip assumption and 2) the interlaminar fracture model. The yield-slip assumption, based on Kelly and Tyson [10], assumes that the shear stress in the matrix is uniform along the overlap length. The tensile strength X_t of the unit cell and thus of the composite can then be approximated by

$$X_t = \frac{L_{Brick} \cdot S_{Mortar}}{T_{Brick}} \quad (1)$$

using the shear strength of the mortar material S_{Mortar} , and neglecting the mortar thickness as well as its contribution to the strength.

The interlaminar fracture model is based on the linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) theory. Applying this theory to our problem, it results that a mode II interface crack between two orthotropic solids advances when its energy release rate is larger than the critical energy release rate G_{IIc} of the interface material. The energy release rate of the crack is, amongst others, dependent on the loading conditions. Following the derivation of Hutchinson [11] for an interfacial crack in a bilayer, the tensile stress at which the crack propagates and hence the composite tensile strength X_t is

$$X_t = \sqrt{\frac{E_{Brick} \cdot G_{IIc}}{t_{Overlap}}} \quad (2)$$

using the elastic modulus of the brick E_{Brick} in the loading direction. It is interesting to note that the tensile strength of the composite is independent of the overlap length in the second approximation, whereas the first approximation states that the strength increases proportionally with the overlap length.

A parametric study of varying brick sizes and mortar constitutive laws conducted by Pimenta and Robinson [4] revealed that these approximations of the overlap strength can be regarded as two boundary cases whose applicability depends on the characteristic aspect ratio of the bricks α , defined as

$$\alpha = L_{Brick} / T_{Brick} \quad (3)$$

The strength of the overlap follows the yield-slip assumption if α is low, or in other words if the bricks are relatively short and thick. In this case, the occurring shear stresses are relatively uniform along the overlap length, hence above assumption is appropriate. On the other hand, for higher aspect ratios, the composite strength converges with the interlaminar fracture model.

They identified two mechanisms for introducing a more gradual failure into the ‘brick-and-mortar’ composites: 1) non-linear matrix response and 2) damage softening and progressive crack formation in the matrix. They found that the non-linear matrix response is active in thick configurations, and that increasing the matrix thickness or the matrix failure strain leads to a more ductile response. Damage softening and crack progression is predominant in slender configurations, where the strength of the composite is governed by fracture mechanics. A damage process zone can develop over a great part of the overlap, leading to progressive loss of stiffness due to damage softening of the mortar.

Based on the two mechanisms discussed, thermoplastics are favourable because 1) Thermoplastics react with a non-linear strain-hardening behaviour when loaded in shear due to entanglements in the polymer network [12], and 2) in general, their fracture toughness is significantly higher than thermosets. These mechanisms that aid a more gradual failure can thus be exploited with a thermoplastic material. We focused on the enhancement of mechanism 2); increased toughness in combination with slender bricks. Thick bricks may optimally exploit non-linear matrix response, however have comparatively low strength and make later industrial applications unfeasible.

The results of the numerical model in conjunction with the corresponding experiments are presented in Section 4.

2.4 Overlap geometries

Two different overlap lengths were chosen for testing, as listed in Table 3. Geometry A was designed such as to obtain maximum non-linearity based on the nominal material properties. The overlap length was adjusted so that the damage process zone of the mortar material fits into the overlap twice (to account for the symmetry of the problem). The overlap length of geometry B was chosen longer in order to enable possible interlaminar crack growth.

Configuration	Aspect ratio α	Overlap length $l_{Overlap}$ (mm)	Brick thickness T_{Brick} (mm)
<i>A</i>	<i>51</i>	<i>14.3</i>	<i>0.56</i>
<i>B</i>	<i>71.4</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>0.56</i>

Table 3: Overview of the overlap geometries tested in this study

A single overlap was placed in the centre of the specimen, whereas the unit cell was repeated along the thickness direction; such as to obtain the stress-strain response of the unit cell overlap in tension. The overlap configuration of geometry A is shown in Figure 2. The brick thickness T_{Brick} was adjusted by blocking two plies with thickness t_{ply} together.

Figure 2: Illustration of the overlap geometry of the tensile specimen

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Specimen preparation

The tensile specimen were prepared by introducing lateral slits in unidirectional pre-impregnated tapes and laying them up so as to obtain the desired overlap geometry, and fusion-bonding them under temperature and vacuum-driven compaction in an oven. During the fusion bonding process, the matrix flows to form the interface between the plies, representing the mortar material which transmits load between the bricks.

Five samples per configuration were manufactured. Tapes from S2 Glass fiber/PA12 provided by Suprem SA, Switzerland, with a width of 50mm, a thickness t_{ply} of 0.28mm and a fiber volume fraction of 55 percent were used. The tapes were cut to a length of 220 mm, and a slit with an offset of half the overlap length as measured from the middle of the tape was introduced using a digital cutter with a pulling knife (Zünd, Switzerland). In each configuration, six tapes were stacked and carefully aligned at the ends, while the overlap was introduced by strategically flipping tapes in the lengthwise direction.

Three stacks were placed beside each other in a vacuum bag. A large steel plate was used as bottom mould and smaller one as caul plate. The bag was evacuated to approximately 50 mbar of absolute pressure and placed in an oven for an hour at 200°C in order to achieve the fusion bonding. We found that consolidating the tapes using vacuum is a good compromise between sufficient laminate quality (e.g. low void content) and avoiding flow-induced fibre orientation disturbance and displacement of the plies. The latter was discovered in previous experiments where the bonding was achieved in a closed mould using a heated press. The stress-strain response in that case was linear-elastic up to failure and the strength was lower than predicted by the numerical model; we attributed this to aforementioned fibre orientation disturbance. This suggests that the mechanical properties of the overlap are sensitive to geometrical deviations. After the bonding process the laminate was allowed to cool at ambient temperature. The tapes were subsequently cut into 15 mm wide and 200 mm long strips using a diamond cutting disc.

Cross-sectional microscopy of the overlap section was performed to check the geometry and detect possible fibre disorientation. We observed that the fibres were relatively undistorted, and that displacement of single plies was at maximum 0.4 mm. The interlaminar region was found to be free of large voids.

3.2 Tensile testing

The tensile tests were conducted on a universal testing machine (Walter + Bai, Switzerland) with a 100kN load cell at a testing speed of 0.5 mm/min. No conditioning was applied to the specimen prior to the testing. A clip-on extensometer (Walter & Bai) with an initial length of 20 mm was used for strain measurement. In the case where the overlap was shorter than the initial length of the extensometer, the extension of the overlap $\Delta l_{Overlap}$ was calculated according to

$$\Delta l_{Overlap} = \Delta l_{Ex} - \frac{F}{A \cdot E_{Brick}} \cdot (l_{oEx} - l_{Overlap}) \quad (4)$$

where Δl_{Ex} is the extensometer extension, F is the measured force, A is the specimen cross-section, and l_{oEx} is the initial length of the extensometer. The initial modulus was determined according to ISO 527 using the 0.005 – 0.025 percent strain secant.

To determine the elastic modulus of the continuous material, i.e. E_{brick} , four of the samples were tested in the continuously reinforced sections using the extensometer. They were loaded to a maximum strain of approximately 0.4 percent previously to the actual overlap tests to avoid any damage in the overlap. The modulus was evaluated according to ISO 527.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Stress-strain response

The stress-strain responses of the overlaps measured during the experiments and obtained from the simulation are shown in Figure 3. The results of configuration A are shown on the left, those of configuration B on the right hand side. The response shows significant non-linearity in both cases.

Figure 3: Measured and predicted stress-strain response of the overlap: configuration A (left) and configuration B (right)

It can be seen that the failure stress of the overlaps is measurably lower than predicted. On the other hand, the maximum strain of the best-performing specimen is higher. This is true for both configurations. The failure stress of both configurations is relatively consistent, whereas the maximum strain varies.

The comparison of the *model* curves for both configurations shows two differences: First, it can be seen that the response of configuration A shows a more pronounced non-linearity before the maximum stress as compared to configuration B. Second, the response of configuration B shows a plateau of constant load due to interlaminar fracture growth, which is not evident in configuration A. Both can be attributed to the difference in overlap length: The overlap length of configuration A was optimised to be twice the size of the damage process zone of the mortar material (see Section 2.4). At the moment of crack initiation, the entire overlap fails. On the other hand, the overlap of configuration B is longer than the damage process zone, hence the overlap is able to carry the applied load even after some fracture growth occurred. This leads to aforementioned stress plateau in configuration B. However, due to the fact that there is more intact material present at the moment of crack formation, the progressive loss of stiffness due to damage softening of the mortar material is less pronounced. This results in a more linear stress-strain response as compared to configuration A.

4.2 Overlap strength and failure strain

The measured and predicted strength, modulus and maximum strain are displayed in Table 4. Mean values and the standard deviation are shown. The initial modulus of the discontinuous composite is 12 % lower than the modulus of the continuous UD plies. Conversely, the measured maximum strength is only one third of the ply strength (the tensile strength of the continuous UD plies is about

1650 MPa according to classical laminate analysis). However, one has to consider that the maximum achievable tensile strength X_{max} of the brick-and-mortar composite is limited to half of the ply tensile strength as a consequence of the discontinuous architecture, hence X_{max} calculates to 825 MPa for the GF/PA12 tapes utilized in this study. At higher stresses the continuous fibers that are bridging the gap at the ends of the overlap will fail. This means that the strength of the tested configurations is about two thirds of what would be theoretically achievable.

Configuration	Experiments			Model		
	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Max. strain (%)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Max. strain (%)
<i>A</i>	42.2 ± 1.6	530 ± 19	2.06 ± 0.29	44.6	716	2.46
<i>B</i>	43.2 ± 1.4	564 ± 27	2.42 ± 0.28	45.4	716	2.61

Table 4: Measured and predicted mechanical characteristics of the tested configurations

A comparison of the measured average strength shows that the strength of configuration B is slightly higher than the one of configuration A, whereas the model predicts the same strength for both configurations. The maximum strain of configuration B is notably higher than configuration A. This is consistent with the predictions, and can be regarded as an increase in ductile behavior.

Figure 4 shows the composite strength as a function of the brick aspect ratio. The interface strength criterion is calculated according to (1), and the interface toughness criterion according to (2). The strength of the bricks with a very low aspect ratio as predicted by the numerical model approaches the prediction made by the interface strength criterion. On the other hand, for bricks with an aspect ratio greater than 50, the strength predicted by the model coincides with the fracture mechanics approximation. In between, a transition occurs, which can be captured with the aid of the model.

Figure 4: Composite strength as a function of brick aspect ratio, comparison between model and experiments

Independent of the aspect ratio, the predicted strength of the discontinuous composite is lower than the maximal achievable strength X_{max} . Figure 4 shows that the strength of high aspect-ratio configurations is limited by the interface fracture toughness, as described by equation (2). In order to achieve the maximum possible strength, one would need to increase the fracture toughness of the mortar material or decrease the brick thickness T_B .

5 DISCUSSION

All measured curves in Figure 3 show a highly non-linear behavior. The stiffness vastly decreases in the region close before failure, almost up to zero in some cases. This probably occurs due to damage softening in the mortar material. A slight increase in stress leads to a large increase in strain. Due to

that, the maximum strain of the discontinuous composite appears to be much more sensitive to variations than the strength. A feasible reason for the large variance in strain could be small deviations in the overlap geometry or local material and/or interface properties, as also stated in [7].

The results show a discrepancy regarding strength between model and experiments. The strength of the measured overlaps is notably lower than predicted. We attribute this to a mismatch in mechanical properties of the mortar material, since the strength appears to be relatively insensitive to minor local geometric deviations. The nominal properties for the mortar material were chosen based on literature, not on actual measurements. To quantify this hypothesis, we made different adaptations to the nominal mortar material model in the simulation, as listed in Table 5. The results of the model and the experimental results of configuration A are compared in Figure 5.

Model	Shear strength	Interface toughness	Strain-hardening	Overlap length
<i>Nominal</i>	<i>45 MPa</i>	<i>3 kJ/m²</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>14.3 mm</i>
<i>a</i>	<i>-20 %</i>			
<i>b</i>		<i>-20 %</i>		
<i>c</i>	<i>-20 %</i>	<i>-20 %</i>		
<i>d</i>			<i>no</i>	
<i>e</i>				<i>-2 mm</i>
<i>f</i>	<i>24 MPa</i>	<i>2 kJ/m²</i>	<i>no</i>	

Table 5: Overview of the modifications of the nominal mortar material model

The strength of the discontinuous composite decreases in all cases, as would be expected with reduced material properties. It is evident that a 20 % decrease of the toughness has a stronger influence on the strength than the same decrease of the shear strength. This is likely because the aspect ratio of the overlaps is relatively high, and the composite strength is governed by the toughness rather than by the shear strength. On the other hand, a decrease in the shear strength magnifies the non-linearity before the possible initiation of an interface crack. Removing the strain-hardening regime in the constitutive behaviour has almost no influence on the response, as the curve is coincident with the nominal model. These findings agree with observations made by Pimenta and Robinson [4].

Figure 5: Comparison of the stress-strain response of the experiments and various model predictions based on different mortar material modifications

A reduction in the overlap length of 2mm also leads to a very slight decrease in strength. However, it is unlikely that this is the reason for the discovered discrepancy, since the overlap length was controlled to within 0.4 mm.

Although a decrease in nominal properties of about 20% led to lower strength, a discrepancy between model and experiments remains. Model f was adjusted manually to give a reasonable fit to the response of the experimental data. A bilinear material law was considered for simplicity. It is interesting to see that the experiments show a higher strain than predicted when the response of the model fits the measured one.

We conclude that a mismatch between the actual properties of the mortar and those used in the simulation play a part in the discovered discrepancy. It may be that the interlaminar shear strength and the fracture toughness were not fully developed during the fusion bonding process utilised in this study, possibly as a consequence of the low pressure used for consolidation. This could be verified by measuring the *in situ* interlaminar shear strength and fracture toughness of the laminate. However, it does not fully answer the problem, since it was not possible to fit the response of the experiments as well as the maximum strain by reducing the mechanical properties in the model. A possible reason might be an uncertainty that arises from assumptions made in the modelling proposed in [4] in conjunction with thermoplastic materials; the softening behavior of the mortar is assumed to follow linear elastic fracture mechanics. It might be interesting to review the applicability of this assumption to ductile materials. It is worthy to note that the model predictions fitted well the response of carbon-epoxy discontinuous composite [7].

We found that the interface fracture toughness is the dominant property with respect to the strength of brick-and-mortar composites with slender bricks. The strength of configurations with short and thick bricks is governed by the interface shear strength. It would be interesting to investigate which of these competing properties is prevailing with regards to chip-based random discontinuous composites, since it is not obvious whether the chips can be regarded slender or thick due to fact that the overlap lengths between adjacent chips and the chip orientation is distributed randomly. In addition, it has become apparent that the maximum strain achievable in a brick-and-mortar composite is sensitive to geometric deviations or imperfections. This may also have an effect on the stress-strain response of chip-based discontinuous composites due to their random nature.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Composites with discontinuous 'brick-and-mortar' architecture, consisting of conceptually stiff load-carrying bricks connected by a mortar material, were treated in this study. The bricks were composed of unidirectional pre-impregnated tapes with a thermoplastic matrix, and a very thin interface of thermoplastic material represented the mortar. The problem was simplified to a unit cell containing a single overlap between two bricks, where the stresses between the bricks are transferred purely by shear in the mortar material. Experimental results showed that it is possible to create a highly non-linear stress-strain response using thermoplastic composite materials in an ordered discontinuous architecture. The non-linearity occurs due to damage softening of the mortar material in the interface between the discontinuous plies (bricks), which leads to gradual loss of stiffness.

A numerical model available from literature, which is based on the shear-lag theory, was used to predict the stress-strain response of the overlap. The predictions were compared to the experimental results. We found that a discrepancy between the model and the experiments exists; the predicted strength was notably higher than the measured one. On the other hand, the maximum strain in the experiments exceeded that of the predictions. We partly attribute this to a mismatch in the mechanical properties of the mortar material; hence we quantified this assumption by adapting the properties in the model. However, no set of properties was found so that both the predicted response and the maximum strain fit the experiments well.

The model proved useful in studying the influence of different mortar material properties on the stress-strain response of the composite. The interlaminar fracture toughness was identified as the most important parameter regarding the strength of brick-and-mortar composites with slender bricks (high aspect ratio). Discontinuous composites with a thermoplastic matrix material hence have a clear advantage over thermoset materials in this respect due to their inherently higher toughness. Combining the advantages of thermoplastic matrix composites with the design freedom of random discontinuous chip-based composites can enable the development of complex load-introduction parts with increased strength and ductility.

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